

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: DIANE

FIRST NAME: MPH0

PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401D

COURSE CODE: DEPI

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American versus British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style guide and why it is needed (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401D period one course pack focused on essential guidance for both international academics and professionals in paper writing. It is a broad module that serves as a foundational resource, entailing key aspects such as essay composition, punctuation, plagiarism avoidance, and adherence to style conventions. Remarkably, it helps students distinguish between US and UK English usage, promoting constancy throughout their writing. Moreover, this course pack offers insight into the instructor's paper review process and utilization of response paper templates and explores advanced features like the "Styles" menu and the "Review" tab. In addition, this course pack provides a preview of upcoming topics and methodologies. It serves as a vigorous foundation for continued academic and professional growth, offering a foretaste of the strategies and expectations of future coursework.

Specifically, chapter one of the course pack covers essay composition. It entails a general overview of the basics of essay writing, the steps for writing a good essay, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2024, 7-14). "There are many types of

essays, but we will discuss essays intended for academic purposes in this chapter” (EUCLID 2024, 7). ACA-401D period one course pack defines academic essay or scholarly writing as “nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work (EUCLID 2024, 7). Examples of academic writing highlighted in the course pack include research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monographs; conference paper; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students’ presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above.

Chapter two of the course pack deals with punctuation. It discusses all the punctuation marks, the examples of how punctuation marks, and the differences between correct and incorrect punctuation (15-23). When using punctuation, the general rule is that use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2024, 16). Examples of punctuations include an apostrophe (which can be used to indicate possession and that letters have been omitted) and ellipsis... (which can be used to show that some text is missing, usually from a quotation (EUCLID 2024, 17 & 22). Chapter 3 of the course pack discusses American versus British English (24-32). This chapter deals with making one understand both American and British English as well as highlighting the differences between US & UK English. American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English" (cf. British English) largely due to various factors such as population size, the wealth of the US, the magnitude of higher education, and the international political and economic position of the US (EUCLID 2024, 25). “American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English” (EUCLID 2024, 25). General categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) include different pronunciation, although same spelling, different spelling, although same pronunciation and same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation (EUCLID 2024, 25&26). Chapter four of the ACA-401D Period one course pack focuses on plagiarism (33-39). This chapter pays attention to what plagiarism is and how it can be avoided. The chapter also looks into citation and paraphrasing. The method of inserting footnotes using MS Word is also discussed in Chapter 4. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information, and citation is a method used to indicate where a piece of information came from. Paraphrases are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written on your own (EUCLID 2024, 34). Chapter five of the ACA-401D Period one course pack deals with the style guide and why it is needed (40-42). A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style can encompass many different aspects like preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, and depth of treatment of a subject. A style guide should be an invaluable tool for any writer, but particularly for the freelance writer. Freelance writers should continually develop style guides for each customer or publication type that they work (EUCLID 2024, 40-42).

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first thing that caught my attention as I was starting this period one was to note that there are many types of essays, even though essays intended for academic purposes are only those discussed in this chapter. ACA-401 course pack further highlights that academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing that is produced as part of academic work (EUCLID 2024, 7). When I read the course pack, it gives pleasure to note that academic essays seek to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence, of which it was something I was not aware of. I have never imagined that research papers and essays share many similarities, including structure, thesis statements, critical thinking, and formal writing. In the basic steps taken in writing an academic essay, it is stated that it is best to start as early as possible so as to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It is never advisable to procrastinate (EUCLID 2024, 7). This is an eye-opener because, as academicians, we tend to relax and ultimately get caught off guard when the submission date is overdue. This ends up compromising the quality of our essays. The course pack clearly stipulates the benefits of thorough research on the topic you want to write about. In the course pack, it is mentioned that while reading about the topic, you should answer the following question: What do I already know about the topic? What do I need to read and know to write the essay? Is this material useful to my topic/argument? Can I use this material to support my answer? (EUCLID 2024, 8).

This clearly indicates that, by conducting thorough research, writers can develop a deeper understanding of their topic, create credibility, ensure accuracy, inspire creativity, and support their arguments. Organizing your ideas forms a very important component of essay writing. When your ideas become more developed, it is now time to write an essay plan that will help you work out how to answer the question and how the essay will be structured. When drawing a plan, you should factor in the following:

Decide on a possible answer to the question (in terms of the research you did), Select the information you will use to answer the question and, look through your notes and choose examples to provide evidence to support your answer, decide which points you will discuss and in which order to write the above points in a sketch form as this will be your essay plan (EUCLID 2024, 8). I used to wonder why I had often obtained low grades in essay writing. But now, after studying this course pack, I have come to the conclusion that an important component of a strong essay is the presence of well-developed ideas in the essay's body paragraphs. Essays often receive poor grades because the ideas are not developed enough. So, it is important to develop an idea by supporting it, discussing its significance, and showing how it connects to the rest of your essay and thesis statement. If you can do all three of these things consistently, you will find yourself writing strong, well-developed paragraphs and papers (EUCLID 2024, 8).

The way the course pack formatted the structure of the essay made me understand the real meaning of an essay. This is because I now understand the link between the introduction, body and conclusion. I am now able to realize that the three parts complement each other very well. This means that if any of the components is not well written, it

compromises the flow and the quality of the whole essay. The course pack also emphasizes the need for all academic essays to contain references. It is through references that plagiarism would be guarded against. Plagiarism is a serious academic offense. (EUCLID 2024, 11). The fact that Euclid University takes the issue of plagiarism seriously makes me comfortable studying with confidence because the qualifications acquired by means of plagiarism are fake. I am optimistic that the University also utilizes various plagiarism-tracking applications such as Turnitin.

The course pack brought in a very crucial point of editing your essay before handing in. According to the course pack, essays improve dramatically with careful editing (EUCLID 2024, 11). I really concur with the statement because a well-edited work with minimal errors indicates that the writer takes his work very seriously. PhD is deemed the highest level of qualification one can reach, and it will be embarrassing to read an essay written by a PhD student with many grammatical and spelling errors.

Handing in the essay is one critical step that must be given thorough consideration because once handed, the essay will be assessed for final grading. According to the course pack, it is essential to read the course guidelines and follow them. Find out how the lecturer/tutor would like assignments presented and ensure you comply with the requirement (EUCLID 2024, 12). I like the fact that the course clearly stipulates important points to be considered before handing in the essay. For instance, you are to ensure that your essay is formatted correctly. You ought to use double-line spacing, a readable font (size 12 at least), number pages and set wide margins (EUCLID 2024, 12).

3) PUNCTUATION

According to the course pack, it is advisable to use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2024, 16). I have read numerous articles and books with long sentences and packed with punctuation. I have observed that I hardly finish reading such kinds of books and articles because they sound boring and tiring. Now, responding to this chapter, I really appreciate the fact that almost all the punctuations have been discussed. However, some of the examples given are either not very clear or are not straightforward because they are too summarized or written in a short form. I hope that when the course pack is revised, the author will come up with simple examples to ease understanding. Secondly, I appreciate that the author has included almost all punctuation, but at the same time, I feel that he could have focused more on punctuation that is commonly used but not normally used properly. Such punctuation may include apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colon and semicolons, ellipses, and Quotation marks. Lastly, I wish the author could identify an article, report or book that utilized most of the punctuation and use it as a sample or example in the course pack. But all in all, I give credit to the author of the course pack because the content is of a high standard.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

In the introduction of the course pack, it is well stipulated that American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II, parallel to the growth of U.S. political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide. American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English" (cf. British English) largely due to various factors such as population, wealth, magnitude of Higher education, global mass media and media technology influence, culture, economic and political position (EUCLID 2024, 25)

Historically, when considering an "open door" policy for foreigners, America is generally considered to be more open than Britain due to its long history of large-scale immigration and the "Open Door" policy, symbolized by the Statue of Liberty, which encourages people from all over the world to come to the United States. This open-door policy encourages people from different continents, such as Africa, to be more familiar with American English compared to British English. Even though we are using British English in Botswana because we were a British colony, American English is still dominating because most of Batswana further their studies in the United States of America. In addition, there are many humanitarian and charity organizations in Botswana that come from America compared to those coming from Britain. The interaction between these organizations and Batswana somehow promotes the use of American English.

The course pack mentioned that "American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English" (EUCLID 2024, 25). The above statement is very accurate because in Botswana and most of the African countries, it is very difficult to differentiate between spoken American and British English. The slight differences can only be spotted in written English.

5) PLAGIARISM

"Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID 2024, 34). The course pack goes further to cite examples of plagiarism. Such examples include taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34).

Critically analysing the description of plagiarism and examples cited in the course pack, I can attest that we plagiarise on a daily basis, either aware or unaware. I have also noticed that, at some point, we do not follow the right referencing styles, hence making it difficult to confirm the source. I acknowledge the fact the course pack clearly supports my point that citations should be done correctly. "In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using" (EUCLID 2024, 34). Secondly, I had wished that the course pack could have stipulated

measures that could be taken against those who plagiarise. Thirdly, the course pack should discuss plagiarism checkers such as Turnitin.

I, however, appreciate and give credit to the author of the course pack because it discusses concepts and subjects that help avoid or reduce plagiarism if they are taken into consideration. First and foremost, the course pack looks into the issue of citation, described as “Method used to indicate where a piece of information came from” (EUCLID 2024, 34). The course pack further highlights important concepts you will need to be aware of, such as in-text citations, quotations, and paraphrasing. The in-text citation refers to “Citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself” (EUCLID 2024, 35). Quotations are the exact words of an author, while paraphrases are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words (EUCLID 2024, 36). From my own perspective, the course pack has described paraphrases in the best possible way. I have also observed that most authors paraphrase and fail to acknowledge the source. In other words, most plagiarism is committed in the name of paraphrasing. Most authors re-write other people’s works through paraphrasing and fail to give credit to original authors.

6) STYLE GUIDE AND WHY WE NEED IT

First of all, I would like to applaud the author of the course pack because he is very clear that even though EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), other internationally recognized Rules are fine (EUCLID 2024, 41). This is a clear indication that Euclid University recognizes the importance of other authors in the field of academic writing. EUCLID also recommends using American English, but both versions are obviously accepted. Secondly, as I was studying this course pack about style guides, I have learned that style guides are what makes a document either interesting or boring, successful or unsuccessful. This is because the style guide ensures consistency across all communications, strengthening brand identity and tone, improving collaboration by providing a clear reference point, saving time by eliminating repetitive decision-making, and enhancing professionalism by maintaining a unified voice across all platforms, ultimately leading to better brand recognition and customer trust. Thirdly, having studied the course pack about style guides and why we need them, I am now able to establish why some books and articles have millions of followers, whereas others do not have. I have noticed that good writers make use of a style guide checklist before publishing their works. According to the course pack, style is much more than just the correct punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary usage. Style can encompass many different aspects such as preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US, for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology and the use of symbols voice (EUCLID 2024, 41).

7) CONCLUSION

Despite the fact that period one has consumed almost 60% of my study time, I can confidently confess that this course pack has laid a very crucial foundation for my studies.

Period one has served as a vigorous groundwork for continued academic and professional growth. It has offered insight into the approaches and expectations of future coursework. This period covered key aspects which are very crucial in academic writing such as essay composition, punctuation, plagiarism avoidance, and adherence to style conventions. Remarkably, it assisted me in differentiating between US and UK English, thereby promoting constancy throughout my academic writing. “Moreover, this course pack offers insight into the instructor's paper review process, showcasing exemplary responses to student submissions” (EUCLID 2024, 3).

I, however, believe that face-to-face interaction is necessary between the instructor and the student because it can significantly benefit the student by fostering a stronger sense of connection, improving engagement, enhancing communication, facilitating real-time feedback, and providing a more personalized learning experience, even within a virtual environment. The course pack is a bulk document packed with challenging concepts that need some further clarification from the instructor. At some point, I felt a bit discouraged, especially when I did not understand some of the concepts. Some topics are too summarised, making them a bit difficult to understand straight away. In the future, when the course pack is revised, it needs to be simplified so that new learners can adapt easily.

REFERENCES

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